

1:3 Dipolar Cycloaddition of Benzonitrile Oxide on to Cinnamyl Arylamines

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Addition of Benzonitrile oxide onto various multiple bonds has been described¹. Benzonitrile oxide is also known to react with active hydrogen compounds. Little attention has been paid towards addition onto dipolarophiles with more than one potential site. Addition of Benzonitrile oxide to $>C=N^-$ rather than $>C=C<$ in conjugated imines has already been reported by us². This communication describes reaction of $>C=C<$ in the presence of N-H. The cinnamyl aryl amines were prepared by the reduction of cinnamal arylamines by Sodium borohydride as described earlier³.

Benzonitrile oxide prepared *in situ* by the usual method reacted with cinnamyl aniline in ether to give an addition product m.p. 132° in 70% yield. Structure (I) has been assigned to the addition compound on the basis of elemental analysis IR, N.M.R. and Mass Spectrum.

N.M.R. Spectrum in $CDCl_3$ 60 Mc/s indicated in addition to fifteen aromatic protons, five protons signals as under : 1H at 4.37 τ as doublet, assigned to $H_{(a)}$? 1H at 6.1 τ as multiplet assigned to $H_{(b)}$, 3H at 6.45 τ as multiplet assigned to $H_{(c)(d)}$. One of the three protons exchanged with deuterium on shaking with D_2O . Mass Spectrum indicated the fragmentation pattern with major peaks assigned to the structures (II), (III) and (IV).

1a. P. Raja Gopalan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, **45**, 5525.

b. R. Huisgen, *Angew Chem. Int. Ed.*, 1963, 563.

2. N. Singh, J. S. Sandhu and Suresh Mohan, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, **42**, 4453.

3. N. Singh, J. S. Sandhu and Suresh Mohan, *Chem. and Ind. (London)*, 1969, 585.

Benzonitrile oxide reacted with other cinnamyl aryl amines to give analogous compounds the characteristics of which are reported in Table-I.

TABLE I

Sr. No.	X	m.p. of dihydro product	m.p. of Isoxozoles	Yield %	Solvent of cryst	Analysis	
						Calculated N%	Found N%
1.	H	20°(135)*	133	80	Methanol	8.54	8.47
2.	<i>m</i> -NO ₂	115-6	148	82	Benzene Pet. ether	11.26	11.18
3.	<i>p</i> -Cl	80	182	78	Benzene	7.72	7.67
4.	<i>p</i> -Br	89-90	145	74	Benzene	6.88	6.81
5.	<i>p</i> -CH ₃	39-40(140)*	170	67	Excess methanol	8.18	8.06
6.	<i>o</i> -CH ₃	71	198	62	Excess methanol	8.18	8.04

* Melting point of the picrates.

EXPERIMENTAL

The conjugated imines were prepared by condensing equimolar quantities of cinnamic aldehyde with appropriate amines in methanol.

The Cinnamyl arylamines were prepared by the reduction of cinnamylidene anilines in methanol with excess of sodium borohydride. The reaction was left over for 24 hrs after which excess of sodium borohydride was decomposed. The products were extracted with ether and crystallised from methanol.

Preparation of benzhydroxalmoyl chloride: Benzhydroxalmoyl chloride was prepared by the method of O.Piloty. α -Benzaldoxime was taken in CHCl₃ or CCl₄ and dry chlorine was passed through it. After the removal of the solvent under vacuum benzhydroxymoyl chloride is obtained as a thick liquid which solidifies on excessive cooling m.p. 42-46°.

Reaction of nitrile oxide with cinnamylarylamines: In a 250 ml. conical flask a solution of cinnamylaniline (2.09 gm; 0.01 mole) in ether (100 ml) was cooled and a solution Benzhydroxamoyl chloride (1.1 gm; 0.01 mole) in ether (20 ml) was added to it. The sol. was kept

at 0° for sometime after which triethylamine (1.2 ml) in ether (20 ml) was added at a very slow rate with continuous shaking. After the addition, reaction was left at 0° for 1 hr, Ether layer was filtered and the residue was washed with dry ether. The ethereal layer was evaporated which gave crystalline compound (2.5 gm, 80%) having m.p. 130°. This on further crystallisation from methanol showed a m.p. 133°.

If in the above experiment, triethylamine was replaced by 14% sodium hydroxide, same product was obtained in almost same yield.

Analysis of $C_{20}H_{20}N_2O$	C	H	N%
Calc.	80.50	6.09	8.54
Found	80.39	6.02	8.47

If in the above experiment, two moles of benzhydroxamyl chloride and triethylamine or 14% sodium hydroxide were used, same product was obtained in the above mentioned yield.

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